

Paraphrase of the concept emotion and feeling

Lakitu and the questionblock from the game Mario Kart look analogical to emotion and feeling, as well as active - and passive adjective in the English language (Mario Kart DS, esl lounge student). An example of an active - and a passive adjective is damaging and damaged. A damaging car means a car that causes damage. A damaged car means a car that has damage caused by something else. Paraphrasing the concept emotion and feeling is saying active - and passive emotion. There are three basic emotions: ecstasy, admiration, loathing. It's unclear if every emotion can be both active and passive, how many emotions there are in total and if emotion can dilute.

To answer what emotions there are, this paper doesn't reinvent the wheel but swaps some spokes of Plutchnik's Wheel of Emotions and renames some (fig. 1). Plutchnik's Wheel of Emotions 1.0's source is the article by Nielek et al (Nielek et al.). Love is not an emotion in Plutchnik's Wheel of Emotions 2.0, because love is benefit effect of symbiosis. Love is part of a set which contains love, apathy and hate. Apathy is no effect of symbiosis. Hate is harm effect of symbiosis. Love in Plutchnik's Wheel of Emotions 1.0 is renamed to euphoria in Plutchnik's Wheel of Emotions 2.0. It's avant-garde to state that there are three basic emotions and it's anachronic to state that there are six basic emotions which are sadness, happiness, fear, anger, surprise and disgust (UWA).

Borderline personality disorder is renamed to Emotion regulation disorder (UvA). Philosopher Spinoza states that the power to moderate and restrain the affects, i.e. emotions, can be present or absent (Grayling). The paraphrase active - and passive emotion could contribute to a better therapeutical relationship. Furthermore, the analogy Mario Kart could trigger research. Both for use as practise to gain emotion regulation and use as practise to test theories of emotion. There is a host of different and often opposing emotion theories both in philosophy and psychology (Fulford et al.).

Fig. 1: Plutchnik's Wheel of Emotions 2.0

loathing		
grief		
vigilance		
euphoria		

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